

Research Article

Antagonistic effects of lactobacilli with anti-oxidative activity against *Helicobacter pylori* infection in mice

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Abstract: The strains of *Lactobacillus gasseri* Chen and *L. plantarum* were evaluated to determine their antagonistic activity against *H. pylori* in vivo, using *L. rhamnosus* GG as a positive control. By analyzing their anti-oxidant activities, these two lactobacilli were found to scavenge α, α -diphenyl- β -picrylhydrazyl and the reactive hydroxyl radical and to have reducing activity. In a mouse model, *H. pylori* infection increased urease activity in the stomach, induced moderate inflammation in the gastric tissue, decreased the level of glutathione, and increased the level of malondialdehyde in the liver and stomach. However, pretreatment with lactobacilli reduced the urease activity in the stomach, decreased the levels of *H. pylori* colonization, alleviated the moderate inflammation in the gastric tissue, increased the level of GSH, and decreased the level of MDA in the liver and stomach. These findings suggested that lactobacilli with anti-oxidant activity could help to alleviate the symptoms of *H. pylori* infection.

Keywords: *Helicobacter pylori*; Lactobacilli; Anti-oxidant; Oxidant stress

Introduction

Helicobacter pylori is a gram-negative, extracellular and microaerophilic human gastric pathogen that infects more than half of the world's human population and causes chronic gastritis, peptic ulcers, and gastric cancer (Dunn, 1997). The pathogenesis of *H. pylori* relies on its persistence in a harsh environment, which includes acidity, peristalsis, and attack by phagocytic cells and the reactive oxygen species (ROS) that they release (Mc Gee D J. , 1999). When activated, phagocytic

leukocytes that release ROS are recruited to the gastric mucosa during infection and constitute an obvious source of oxidative stress (Davies et al., 1994; Zhang et al., 1997). Oxidative damage plays a significant pathological role in human diseases, such as cancer, emphysema, cirrhosis, atherosclerosis, and arthritis (Halliwell, 1984). Recent studies have demonstrated that *H. pylori* can induce oxidative stress and increase the levels of ROS in gastric epithelial cells, which can lead to alterations in epithelial proliferation and oxidative DNA damage that may be one of the mechanisms that results in the apoptosis associated with infection (Ding et al., 2007). Other studies have demonstrated that *H. pylori* itself also generates ROS (Nagata et al., 1998) that accumulates in the gastric epithelial cells (Bagchi et al., 1996; Bagchi et al., 2002). Therefore, substances with anti-oxidative activity may help the human body to reduce oxidative damage and provide an adjuvant therapy for diseases caused by *H. pylori*.

Lactobacilli are considered to be beneficial microorganisms and have been widely used as dietary adjuncts in cultured dairy foods and other fermented products. The potential benefits of lactic acid bacteria for human health include the improvement of lactose intolerance, the prevention of intestinal infections, the reduction of serum cholesterol, the stimulation of the immune system, and anti-carcinogenic and anti-oxidative effects (Li et al., 2014). Recent studies have shown that various strains of lactic acid bacteria exhibit anti-oxidative activity both *in vitro* and *in vivo* (Ito et al., 2001; Lapointe et al., 2006; Terahara et al., 2001; Truusalu et al., 2010). The anti-oxidative mechanisms of lactic acid bacteria include the ability to chelate metal ions, the scavenging of reactive oxygen species (such as hydrogen peroxide, the hydroxyl radical and the α,α -diphenyl- β -picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) free radical), enzyme inhibition (such as superoxide dismutase), and reducing activity (Lin and Yen, 1999). Therefore, lactobacilli are potential candidates for the production of functional foods as natural anti-oxidant supplements.

Recent studies have shown that lactobacilli can inhibit the growth of *H. pylori*, urease activity, adherence in the gastric mucosa, and alleviate inflammation (Cui et al., 2010; Sgouras et al., 2004). In addition, the oxidative stress caused by *H. pylori* promotes gastric inflammation and infection, and it has been reported that lactobacilli alleviates the gastric inflammation caused by *H. pylori* and decreases the levels of gastric malondialdehyde (MDA) and apoptotic epithelial cells in rats (Sunanliganon et al., 2012). Hutt (Hutt et al., 2009) reported that a synbiotic product containing an anti-oxidative probiotic strain may be useful in the reduction of systemic oxidative stress in *H. pylori* infection. In this study, the ability of *Lactobacillus gassri* Chen and *L. plantarum* 18 that

have anti-*H. pylori* effects *in vitro* (Chen et al., 2012; Chen et al., 2010) were evaluated for their antagonistic activities against *H. pylori* and their related anti-oxidative abilities *in vivo*. *L. rhamnosus* GG, the antioxidative activity of which has been validated, was used as a positive control.

Materials and methods

Bacterial Stains and Culture Conditions

H. pylori standard strain SS1 (Sydney strain 1) was obtained from the Culture Collection of Microorganisms, Jiangnan University of Wuxi, Jiangsu, and was cultured on Colombia base agar (Oxoid, Basingstoke, UK) supplemented with 7% sheep blood and 0.4% *H. pylori* selective supplement (Oxoid, Basingstoke, UK) at 37 °C in 5% carbon dioxide for 3–5 days.

The *L. rhamnosus* GG (LGG), *L. gassri* Chen (LG Chen), and *L. plantarum* 18 (LP18) strains were also obtained from the Culture Collection of Microorganisms, Jiangnan University of Wuxi, Jiangsu, and were cultured in Man-Rogosa-Sharpe broth, and incubated in an anaerobic box at 37 °C for 24 h. The concentration of the bacteria was regulated at 1×10^9 CFU/mL.

Preparation of Intact Cells and the Intracellular Cell-free Extract of Lactobacilli

Cells of three strains of lactobacilli were harvested by centrifugation at 6000 rpm for 10 min after 18 h of incubation at 37 °C. For the preparation of intact cells, cell pellets were quickly washed twice in phosphate buffer solution (PBS; 0.85% NaCl, 2.68 Mm KCl, 10 mM Na₂HPO₄, and 1.76 mM KH₂PO₄) and then re-suspended in PBS. For the preparation of the intracellular cell-free extracts, cell pellets were quickly washed twice in deionized water and then resuspended in deionized water followed by ultrasonic disruption (VCX500, Sonics & Materials). Sonication was performed at five 1-min intervals in an ice bath. Cell debris was removed by centrifugation at 8000 rpm for 10 min, and the resulting supernatant represented the intracellular cell-free extract. Total cell numbers were adjusted to 10^9 CFU/mL prior to the preparation of intact cells and cell-free extracts.

Determination of α,α -diphenyl- β -picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) Radicals of Lactobacilli

The scavenging of DPPH by the three strains of lactobacilli was analyzed by a modified method of Shimada et al. (Kazuko. Shimada, 1992) and Lin (Lin and Chang, 2000); 0.8 mL of intact cells or intracellular cell-free extract and 1 mL of freshly prepared DPPH solution (0.2 mM in methanol) were mixed and allowed to react for 30 min. Blank samples contained either PBS or deionized

water. The scavenged DPPH was then monitored by measuring the decrease in absorbance at 517 nm. The scavenging ability was defined as follows:

$$[1 - A_{517}(\text{sample}) / A_{517}(\text{blank})] \times 100 \%$$

Determination of Hydroxyl Radicals of Lactobacilli

Hydroxyl radicals were determined by a modified method of Avellar et al. (de Avellar et al., 2004) and Wang et al. (Wang et al., 2009). Briefly, 1 mL of 1,10-phenanthroline (0.75 mmol^{-1}), 2 mL of PBS and 1 mL of ferrous sulfate (0.75 mmol^{-1}) were mixed thoroughly. Then, 1 mL of hydrogen peroxide (0.12%) and 1 mL of the intact cells or intracellular cell-free extracts were added. The mixture was incubated at 37 °C for 60 min, and the absorbance was measured at 536 nm. The results were calculated as follows:

$$\text{Hydroxyl radical-scavenging activity (\%)} = (A_s - A_c) / (A_b - A_c) \times 100$$

where A_s represents the absorbance of the sample, A_c represents the absorbance of the control solution containing 1,10-phenanthroline, ferrous sulfate, and hydrogen peroxide, and A_b represents the absorbance of the blank solution containing 1,10-phenanthroline and ferrous sulfate. Salicylic acid (1 mL) or deionized water (blank) was added. The change in absorbance caused by the color change of the salicylic acid was measured at 510 nm.

Reducing Activities of Lactobacilli

The method developed by Lin (Lin and Yen, 1999) was used to evaluate the reducing activity of lactic acid bacteria; 0.5 mL of potassium ferricyanide (1%) were mixed with the same volume of PBS and intact cells or intracellular cell-free extracts. The reaction mixture was incubated at 50 °C for 20 min, then cooled rapidly, and 0.5 mL of TCA (10%) was added; 1.5 mL of upper phase were obtained by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 5 min, and 0.2 mL of ferrous chloride (0.1%) were added. Absorbance was read at 700 nm, and cysteine was used as the standard for the expression of reducing activity.

Infection of C57BL/6 Mice with *H. pylori* SS1 and Administration of Lactobacilli

Fifty female C57BL/6 mice (4 weeks old) were obtained from Shanghai (Shanghai Slac Laboratory Animals Ltd., China). The animals were housed in cages in a controlled animal room (22±2 °C, 50–60% relative humidity, 12-h light-dark cycle with lighting from 7:00 to 19:00) for 3 days, and were then randomly divided five groups. As shown table 1, Group 1 was gavaged with PBS as a negative control. Group 2 was gavaged with *H. pylori* SS1 (250 µL at 10^9 CFU/mL in PBS) 3 times a week (days 1, 3 and 5) at a 1 d interval between inoculations for 2 weeks and were then

gavaged with PBS for 6 months. Groups 3–5 were gavaged with lactobacilli (250 μ L at 10^9 CFU/mL LGG, LP Chen and LP 18 in PBS, separately) for 2 weeks prior to gavage with *H. pylori* SS1 (250 μ L at 10^9 CFU/mL in PBS) and then gavaged with lactobacilli (250 μ L at 10^9 CFU/mL LGG, LP Chen and LP 18 in PBS, separately) for 6 months. The mice were euthanized, and their stomachs were excised and dissected along the lesser curvature, to obtain two equivalent parts. Samples were frozen at -20 °C until their use in the analyses of MDA and GSH levels. All the protocols of animal study were approved by the Ethics Committee of Jiangnan University.

Table 1 Animal experimental design

Group	Duration in weeks		
	0-2	3-4	5-24
Group 1	PBS	PBS	PBS
Group 2	PBS	<i>H.pylori</i>	PBS
Group 3	LGG	<i>H.pylori</i>	LGG
Group 4	LGchen	<i>H.pylori</i>	LGchen
Group 5	LP18	<i>H.pylori</i>	LP18

Animals received PBS and bacteria via tube gavages

H. pylori infection: *H. pylori* SS1 (250 μ L at 10^9 CFU/mL in PBS) 3 times a week (days 1, 3 and 5) at a 1-d interval between inoculations for 2 weeks.

Lactobacilli intervention: LGG, LP Chen and LP 18 (250 μ L at 10^9 CFU/mL once daily).

***H. pylori* Colonization in Gastric Homogenates**

The method developed by Sutton (Philip Sutton, 2000) and Cui (Cui et al., 2010) was used to assess *H. pylori* colonization. A longitudinal segment of the stomach was homogenized using a Pro 200 homogenizer with a 1-cm tip in sterile PBS. Serial dilutions were then plated onto Glax Selective Supplement A agar plates (7% sheep blood, 2.5 μ g/mL amphotericin, 200 μ g/mL bacitracin, 6 μ g/mL vancomycin, 2 μ g/mL nalidixic acid, and 0.5 μ g/mL polymyxin) and incubated under microaerophilic conditions at 37 °C for 72 h.

Urease Assay

The basic urease assay was carried out, as developed by Hazell et al. (HAZELL et al., 1987) and which is commonly used by many laboratories worldwide. Briefly, 150 μ L of urease reagent was placed in the wells of a flat-bottomed 96-well plate, to which 50 μ L of gastric homogenates were added. The wells were covered and incubated for 24 h, and urease positivity was determined by an increase in pH, indicated by a change in color from orange to red.

Histological Examination

A portion of the gastric tissue was fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin solution and embedded in paraffin. The histopathology of blinded 5- μ m sections stained with hematoxylin and eosin was

assessed under light microscopy to examine the degree of gastric inflammation and histopathological changes in the gastric tissue. All sections were examined by an experienced pathologist who was blind to the treatment groups and to the other results of this study. Gastric mucosal lesions were evaluated according to the histological scoring based on the Sydney system. The pathologic characteristics were graded for the degree of neutrophil and mononuclear cell infiltration in the antrum and body as follows: Score 1, mildly multifocal; score 2, mildly widespread or moderately multifocal; score 3, mildly widespread and moderately multifocal or severely multifocal; score 4, moderately widespread; score 5, moderately widespread and severely multifocal; and score 6, severely widespread (Nolan et al., 2002).

Determination of GSH and MDA Levels

The liver and gastric tissues were removed, washed, and homogenized in ice cold physiological saline to prepare 10% (w/v) homogenates. The homogenates were then centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 10 min at 4 °C to remove cellular residue. The supernatants were collected to measure the levels of GSH activity and MDA. Both assays were conducted according to the instructions of the kits from the Nanjing Jiancheng Bioengineering Institute, China.

Statistical Analyses

The results are expressed as means \pm standard errors. Comparisons were made using the one-way analysis of variance and Fisher's exact probability test.

Results

Antioxidant Activities

Antioxidant activities of lactobacilli were measured by scavenging of reactive DPPH, reactive hydroxyl radical and reducing activity. The results were shown in Fig.1. The three strains of lactobacilli had excellent DPPH scavenging ability in Fig.1-A. Intact cells and intracellular extracts of 10^9 cells of lactobacilli were able to scavenge 45–65% and 30–50%, separately. A significant difference was observed between the three bacterial strains and between the intact cells and the intracellular extracts, with LG Chen showing the highest scavenging rate of DPPH. The hydroxyl radical scavenging rate of intracellular cell-free extracts of LGG was the highest (about 60%), and was more than three times that of LP 18, which had the lowest scavenging rate (about 20%) in Fig. 1-B. The reducing activities of lactobacilli were shown in Fig.1-C. Reducing activity of intact cells of LGG, which had the highest activity equivalent to 120 μ M of cysteine, was more than twice that of LP 18, which had the lowest activity, equivalent to 60 μ M of cysteine. Generally,

the three strains tested demonstrated excellent reducing activity. Above all, these three lactobacilli had well antioxidant activities, and a significant difference was observed between the three live bacterial strains, but not between the intact cells and the intracellular extracts.

Fig. 1. The anti-oxidative activities of intact cells or intracellular extracts of lactobacilli
 A: Scavenging ability of DPPH of intact cells or intracellular extracts of lactobacilli
 B: Scavenging ability of hydroxyl radical of intact cells or intracellular extracts of lactobacilli
 C: Reducing activity of intracellular cell-free extract of lactic acid bacteria
 Values in the same column with different letter superscripts are significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$).

Body Weight, and Food and Water Intake

Body weight was measured every month and was not altered when C57BL/6 mice were treated with lactobacilli. During the first 2 months, the weights of the mice increased, probably due to growth. After 4 months, the weights of the mice remained stable throughout the treatment protocol, and no significant difference was observed among the five groups (Fig. 2). The food and water

intakes of the mice were also evaluated and no significant difference was found among the five groups (Table 2).

Fig. 2. Body weight of mice

Table 2 The take of food and water of the mice and the urease activity of stomach

Group	Food intake (g)	Water intake (mL)	No. of Mice positive/totals Urease
Control	3.1±0.3	5.2±0.7	0/10
<i>H. pylori</i>	2.9±0.3	5.8±1.3	7/10
<i>H. pylori</i> +LGG	3.0±0.3	6.0±1.4	5/10
<i>H. pylori</i> +LGChen	2.8±0.3	5.6±0.7	6/9
<i>H. pylori</i> +LP18	3.5±0.8	5.8±1.1	5/10

H. pylori Colonization in Gastric Homogenates

The degree of *H. pylori* colonization in the gastric mucosa was measured by a colony count. The lactobacilli-pretreated and triple-treated group showed a significant decrease in *H. pylori* density. The *H. pylori* density in the LP 18-pretreated group was lower than that in the *H. pylori* group and was close to that in the PPI triple-treated group (data not shown). The bacterial density in the LGG- and LG Chen-pretreated groups was lower than that in the *H. pylori* group, but this was not statistically significant (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. *H. pylori* colonization in gastric homogenates

Histological Examination

H. pylori infection in mice was determined by the urease test and histopathology. About 70% of the mice in the *H. pylori* treated group showed positive urease activity, but this ratio decreased in the lactobacilli-pretreated groups to about 50% (Table 2). Histopathology in the control group was normal, while there was moderate *H. pylori*- induced inflammation in the *H. pylori*-infected group. Histopathologic evaluation revealed a significant improvement in mucosal inflammation in the gastric area in lactobacilli-treated groups. The score of pathologic characteristics in the gastric mucosa also showed a marked decrease. The score in the LGG-pretreated group was significantly lower than that of the *H. pylori*-treated group ($P \leq 0.05$), and almost similar to the blank control group. The score of the LP18- and LG Chen-pretreated groups was also lower than that of the *H. pylori* group (Figs 4 and 5).

Fig. 4 Histological scores of gastric area in the mice

Fig. 5 Histological image of gastric area in the mice (×200)

A: control groups, B: *H. pylori* infection, extensive inflammation in the mucosal layer, massive mixed cell infiltration (mainly mononuclear); C: LGG+ *H. pylori* group, a few incomplete mucosa; D: LG Chen +*H. pylori* group, a few incomplete mucosa; E: LP18+ *H. pylori* group, a few incomplete mucosa; arrows mean infiltration of inflammatory cells ;(HE, light microscope, × 200).

Determination of GSH and MDA Levels

The level of MDA in the liver was significantly increased in the *H. pylori*-infected compared

with the control group (0.69±0.06 nmol/mg versus 0.86±0.12 nmol/mg protein, respectively; Table 3), whereas there was a significant decrease in the liver MDA level in both of the lactobacilli-pretreated groups. The level of liver GSH increased significantly in the lactobacilli-pretreated groups compared with the *H. pylori*-infected group, but no difference was observed between the *H. pylori*-infected group and the control group. Similar trends of decreasing gastric MDA level and increasing gastric GSH level were observed in the lactobacilli-pretreated groups compared with the *H. pylori*-infected group, but the difference was not statistically significant.

Table 3 The levels of GSH and MDA in the stomach and liver of mice

Group	liver		stomach	
	GSH (mg/gprot)	MDA (nmol/mgprot)	GSH (mg/gprot)	MDA (nmol/mgprot)
Control	1.30±0.20 ^{ab}	0.69±0.06 ^a	6.94±1.79 ^a	0.27±0.04 ^a
<i>H. pylori</i>	1.35±0.08 ^{ab}	0.86±0.12 ^b	4.10±1.06 ^a	0.33±0.06 ^a
<i>H. pylori</i> +LGG	1.84±0.14 ^d	0.75±0.10 ^a	6.20±4.70 ^a	0.23±0.08 ^a
<i>H. pylori</i> +LGChen	1.50±0.15 ^{bc}	0.71±0.10 ^a	4.68±0.81 ^a	0.26±0.04 ^a
<i>H. pylori</i> +LP18	1.25±0.22 ^a	0.73±0.08 ^a	6.12±1.61 ^a	0.27±0.06 ^a

^{abcd}Column means containing different letters are significantly (P < 0.05) different.

Discussion

Lactobacillus is a beneficial microorganism that exists in the gastrointestinal tract, and has a number of functions, such as stimulating the intestinal mucosal barrier, improving the balance between inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines, and establishing a healthy interaction between the host and microbes in the intestinal tract. In recent years, some reports have shown that lactobacilli have anti-oxidant properties *in vitro* and *in vivo*. *Lactobacillus* GG can reduce alcohol-induced intestinal oxidative stress (Thirabunyanon et al., 2009), and *Bifidobacterium catenulatum* ZYB0401 in combination with *L. fermentum* ZYL0401 can decrease the level of MDA and improve the activity of superoxide dismutase in the liver (Gu et al., 2006). *L. fermentum* ME-3 can decrease the levels of peroxidized lipoproteins and enhance total anti-oxidative activity (Park and Hahm, 2005). In this study, the anti-oxidative activities of two strains of lactobacilli (*L. gassri* Chen and *L. plantarum* 18) were evaluated in comparison with those of LGG as a positive control. The results showed that intact cells and intracellular extracts of the three strains had anti-oxidant activities. The rate of DPPH scavenging ranged from 30% to 60%, with LG Chen showing the highest rate. The rate of hydroxyl radical scavenging was 20–60%, with LGG showing the highest

rate. The reducing activity of the three strains ranged from 60 μ M to 120 μ M equivalent of cysteine, and LGG had the highest activity. In general, LGG had the highest anti-oxidant activities of the three strains.

H. pylori, a human pathogen, can survive in the highly acidic environment of the stomach, and can cause gastritis, gastric ulcer and gastric. Moreover, the number of asymptomatic persons infected with *H. pylori* is very large. A triple drug therapy is mainly used to treat the diseases caused by *H. pylori* infection, but it has many side effects, such as diarrhea, diminished appetite and bacterial resistance. Probiotic lactobacilli have been shown to reduce *H. pylori* colonization and decrease *H. pylori*-induced gastric inflammation *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Therefore, lactobacilli have been used as the main probiotics for the treatment or adjuvant treatment of diseases caused by *H. pylori* infection. In this study, similar results were found in all lactobacilli-pretreated groups of mice in which the number of *H. pylori* in the stomach was reduced, the urease activities of *H. pylori* were decreased, stomach pathology was improved and gastric inflammation was alleviated.

Some studies have shown that gastric diseases caused by *H. pylori* infection may be association with *H. pylori*-induced oxidative stress. Cell DNA and tissue damage were induced by ROS and reactive nitrogen species. Bagchi (Zheng et al., 2014) reported that *H. pylori* enhanced the production of ROS and DNA damage in human gastric mucosal cells and that the 87-kDa cytotoxin protein played a primary role in the induction of this oxidative stress and DNA damage. Beil (Beil et al., 2000) reported that *H. pylori* directly decreased cellular concentrations of GSH in gastric epithelial cells, which may be associated with the release of ROS by *H. pylori*. Fosslie (Fosslie, 2001) reported that ROS induced by *H. pylori* induce uncoupling, which can open the membrane pores and activate apoptosis. Pignatelli (Pignatelli et al., 2001) reported that the oxidative stress associated with *H. pylori* infection-induced inflammation was reduced by the eradication of *H. pylori* in a clinical trial. Kimura (Kimura et al., 2001) reported that *H. pylori* vacuolating cytotoxin (*vacA*) impaired the metabolism of GSH in gastric epithelial cells, which weakened the resistance of the cells to oxidative stress and the cellular redox regulation by GSH. Sunanliganon (Sunanliganon et al., 2012) reported that infection with *H. pylori* *cagA*⁺, *vacA*⁺ strains led to elevated levels of gastric MDA. These studies suggested that substances with anti-oxidant activity can help to reduce excessive oxidative stress-associated inflammation. Truusalu et al. (Truusalu et al., 2008) found that *L. fermentum* ME-3 suppressed the excessive oxidative stress-associated inflammation induced by *Salmonella typhimurium* infection in a mouse model, and Yanaka

(Yanaka, 2011) reported that sulforaphane, a natural chemical compound found in broccoli sprouts, protected against oxidative stress and enhanced the repair of the gastric mucosa *in vitro*, and demonstrated anti-inflammatory effects in the gastric mucosa during *H. pylori* infection in mice and humans. Sunanliganon (Sunanliganon et al., 2012) reported that *L. plantarum* B7 significantly improved stomach pathology, and decreased the levels of gastric MDA and apoptotic epithelial cells in rats. Our results were similar, and showed that the level of GSH in the liver and stomach decreased in *H. pylori*-infected mice and the level of MDA increased, whereas in lactobacilli-pretreated mice, the level of GSH in liver and stomach increased and the level of MDA decreased. Moreover, gastric inflammation was alleviated in lactobacilli-pretreated mice. These phenomena indicated that lactobacilli with anti-oxidant activity can help to alleviate the inflammation caused by *H. pylori*.

The mechanisms by which lactobacilli protect against *H. pylori* infection have been confirmed by animal models and by studies *in vitro* (Sgouras et al., 2004): (1) lactobacilli secrete large amounts of organic acids and antimicrobial peptides, such as lactic acid, acetoacetic acid and acetic acid, which can inhibit the growth of *H. pylori*; (2) lactobacilli with a high affinity to gastric epithelial cells could block the adherence of *H. pylori* to the gastric mucosa by competitively combining with the cells in the host; (3) lactobacilli can adjust the immune response after *H. pylori* infection by regulating cytokines, such as interleukin-8 and tumor necrosis factor- α , and blocking the pro-inflammatory pathways (Yang et al., 2012); and (4) other mechanisms, such as changing the microenvironment of the gastric mucosa, reducing oxidative stress and competing for nutrients (Wang and Huang, 2014) may also exist. The mechanism of probiotic therapy on *H. pylori* infection and the change in the relationship between the intestinal flora and anti-oxidative stress are very complex, and further studies are needed for their elucidation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, *L. gassri* Chen and *L. plantarum* 18 showed clear anti-oxidant activities, such as scavenging DPPH and reactive hydroxyl radicals, and reducing activity. In the mouse model, pretreatment with lactobacilli reduced the urease activity in the stomach, decreased the levels of *H. pylori* colonization, and alleviated moderate inflammation in the gastric tissue. Moreover, lactobacilli were able to increase the level of GSH and decrease the level of MDA in the liver and stomach. LGG had the greatest anti-oxidant activity of the three lactobacilli strains tested and *L. rhamnosus* GG pretreated group showed the highest the level of GSH and lowest level of MDA in

the liver and stomach of *H. pylori* infected mice. These results suggested that lactobacilli with anti-oxidant activity help to alleviate *H. pylori* infection. Lactobacilli will be used as probiotic to manufacture dairy products preventing *H. pylori* infection. Next work, the molecular technologies will be used to explain the mechanisms of lactobacilli antagonistic against *H. pylori*.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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